

Optimal Design and Management of Photovoltaic and Energy Storage Systems

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Abstract – This paper discusses the design of a hybrid system of photo-voltaic and battery storage element to cover average residential load with the minimum total cost. Cuckoo search algorithm (CS), mixed linear integer programming (MLIP) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) techniques are used to minimize the total annual cost for residential load in Egypt. By comparing the results after applying the different mentioned methods, MILP was the one which achieved the least Annual cost.

Keywords: Photovoltaic, Energy Storage, Optimization, Cuckoo Search, Mixed Linear Integer Programming, Particle Swarm.

I. Introduction

Renewable energy became one of the most important fields to overcome the effects of traditional energy resources which cause a lot of problems such as global warming, pollution, increase the rate of consumption of these fossil fuels, Carbon Emissions and Climate Change.

Geologists and others whose job is to locate and access these pockets of crude oil are finding it increasingly difficult to locate and extract new sources. Whether we have 1 year or 100 years left of oil, many argue that what is left should remain in the ground because it is not sustainable - it will run out eventually and so we should prepare for a post-fossil fuel world now [1]. On the other hand, consumption was not reduced but also increased, so it becomes necessary to head into renewable energy sources not only in the large scale but also in the small scale in residential applications. This leads to reduce the environmental effects and contributes in lowering the residential load which can reach the level that the production exceeds the consumption and sell to the grid. Among all renewable energy sources, the solar energy is selected for its advantages such as:

1. It will last as long as the sun will last - which is billions of years against the maximum remaining life span that can't exceed 70-80 years, and against the several decades of gas and coal. It is a very flexible energy source and can be used not only in electricity generation, but also in heating water directly and may be used as a source of light [1].
2. It becomes cheaper each day (reduction in capital cost).
3. Silent where no moving parts.
4. Easy to operate & low maintenance.

The only disadvantage is the initial cost so, the main objective of this research to minimize the total cost through the different optimization techniques.

Di Zhu et. al. [2] concluded that the PV systems are promising in making profits for residential usage, but a closer search in the PV power generation characteristics and the power consumption of load is essential to prove the profitability for consumers. To fully utilize the harvested solar energy, PV systems necessitate built-in EES banks to store the excessive energy for later use. In turn, the performance of EES banks has a significant influence on the system efficiency and profitability. An integer linear programming based algorithm has been developed and used to find an optimum, least cost, configuration for a hybrid (wind and photovoltaic) renewable system to satisfy residential demand in selected sites in Egypt [3]. The results prove that the renewable energy projects are making profits for sites, where wind and solar irradiation are abundant, the system is cost effective. But in locations where wind speed is less, the system required the use of more photovoltaic solar panels increasing the system cost. These systems have a payback period greater than 20 years. In [4], average of residential load over year as in Fig. 1 is covered by the system with the different optimization techniques.

Fig. 1 Annual residential load

This paper will be organized as follows: Section 2 presents the solar system components. Section 3 presents the design calculation. The design constrains are presented in section 4, while different minimization methods are presented in Section 5. Section 6 presents the results of applying the optimization methods and finally the paper conclusion is given in section 7.

II. Solar System Components

Fig. 2 shows the configuration of the system under study.

Fig. 2 System under study

II.1. PV Modules

The long-term performance of PV modules is far more stable than most of the traditional electrical systems. The average annual degradation rate of power generation of a PV module, including all its internal circuit breakage cases, is below 1%. Moreover, the PV modules lifetime can exceed 30 years or more [2]. The tilt angle of PV modules is very important especially when PV modules are fixed over the year to gain maximum possible output power over the year not each month. To calculate the optimum tilt of solar panels, the following sum can be used [5]:

$$\text{Optimum fixed year round setting} = 90^\circ - \text{your latitude} \quad (1)$$

Linear approximation is used to calculate the optimal tilt angle [6]:

$$\text{Optimal tilt angle (Deg)} = 3.7 + 0.69 * \left| \text{The latitude of the site (deg)} \right| \quad (2)$$

By trying both methods, the irradiance over the year is more when using the second method than the first one.

II.2. Batteries

Many types of batteries such as Lead Acid batteries, Lithium Ion batteries, Absorbed Glass Mat (AGM) batteries and Nickel based batteries can be used. Two types of batteries were selected LFP (Lithium Ferro Phosphate) and AGM batteries to differentiate between

the both batteries over the long term of the project life time.

II.3. Batteries

There are two main types Pulse Width Modulation (PWM), Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT). MPPT will be used in this study which tracks the maximum power point of the array throughout the day in order to deliver the maximum available solar energy to the batteries or the system. Using MPPT can deliver additional 15-30% more power out of an array versus a PWM controller [3].

II.4. Inverter

This will be used to supply the domestic AC load.

III. Design Calculations

Total annual cost (TAC):

$$TAC = \frac{\sum I_C + O_C - S_V}{N} \quad (3)$$

where I_C is the total Initial cost of the system,
 O_C is the total operating cost of the system,
 S_V is the Salvage Value.
 N is the system life time (25 years).

PV cost [7]:

$$\text{Initial cost } C_{ipv} = c_{ipv} (\$/m^2) * A_{pv} (m^2) \quad (4)$$

where $c_{ipv} (\$/m^2)$ is the initial cost of PV per m^2
 $A_{pv} (m^2)$ is the total Area of PV.

Operating & Maintenance

$$C_{opv} = c_{opv} \left(\frac{\$}{m^2} \right) * A_{pv} (m^2) * \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{1+e}{1+i} \right)^n \quad (5)$$

where $c_{opv} (\$/m^2)$ is the operating cost of PV per m^2 , e is the Escalation rate and i is the interest rate

Salvage value

$$C_{spv} = c_{spv} \left(\frac{\$}{m^2} \right) * A_{pv} (m^2) * \left(\frac{1+f}{1+i} \right)^N \quad (6)$$

where $c_{spv} (\$/m^2)$ is the salvage value of PV per m^2 and f is the Inflation rate

Battery cost (CB) [7]

Initial Cost

$$C_{iB} = c_{iB} \left(\frac{\$}{KW} \right) * P_B (KW) * \sum_{t=1}^{nb} \left(\frac{1+e}{1+f} \right)^{(t-1)N_B} \quad (7)$$

where $c_{iB} \left(\frac{\$}{KW} \right)$ is the initial cost of battery per W
 P_B (kilo Watt) battery capacity
 nb is the number of battery replacement over lifetime (3 for AGM battery & 1 for LFP battery)
 N_B is the life span of storage battery

Operating & Maintenance C_{OB}

$$C_{OB} = C_{OB} \left(\frac{\$}{KW} \right) * P_B (KW) * \sum_{n=1}^{NB} \left(\frac{1+e}{1+i} \right)^n \quad (8)$$

where c_{OB} is the operating & maintenance cost of battery per KW.

Initial cost of inverter (C_{inv}) [7]

$$C_{inv} = c_{iinv} \left(\frac{\$}{KW} \right) * p_{iinv}(kW) \quad (9)$$

where c_{iinv} is the initial cost of inverter per kW.
 p_{iinv} (KW) is the needed inverter power

Initial cost of controller C_{con} [7]

$$C_{cont} = c_{icont} (\$/KW) * p_{cont}(KW) \quad (10)$$

where $c_{icont} (\$/KW)$ is the initial cost of charge controller per kW. And p_{cont} (kW) is the needed charge controller power

$$I_C = c_{ipv} + c_{iB} + C_{inv} + C_{cont} \quad (11)$$

$$O_C = c_{opv} + c_{oB} \quad (12)$$

$$S_v = C_{spv} \quad (13)$$

IV. Design Constraints

Total generated and stored power to cover average load power

$$P_{PV} + P_B \geq P_{load} \quad (14)$$

Total initial cost

$$C_{ipv} + C_{iB} + C_{inv} + C_{cont} \leq B \text{ (BUDGET)} \quad (15)$$

Area constrain (A_{pv}) is determined by available area.

Battery capacity constrain [7]

$$0 \leq P_B \leq P_{BMaxCap} \quad (16)$$

where $P_{BMaxCap}$ is Battery maximum power

Max installed voltage of PV \leq Max rating voltage of controller [3]

$$V_{oc} * N_{pvs} \leq V_{con} \quad (17)$$

Where N_{pvs} Photovoltaic panels in series connection

V_{oc} Photovoltaic panel open circuit voltage

V_{con} Charger controller voltage

Max power STC of PV \leq Max o/p power of controller[3]

$$P_{PVSTC} * N_{pv} \leq \sum P_{ctrl} * N_{ctrl} \quad (18)$$

V. Optimization Methods

V.1. Cuckoo Search (CS) Algorithm

It is a global optimization method based on the behavior of cuckoos and was proposed by Yang & Deb (2009). The CS was inspired by the obligate brood parasitism of some cuckoo species by laying their eggs in the nests of host birds. Some cuckoos develop technique to make cuckoos eggs look like few species host birds in

both pattern and color. This development increases the possibilities of egg to been hatched and not been abandoned, the chosen host nest always be for bird just laid its eggs. Considering that in case the host bird discovers that the egg doesn't belong to it, the host bird either leaves the nest and builds new one or throws the egg from the nest. Generally the cuckoo eggs hatch before the host eggs, once it hatched its first behavior is to throw the other eggs from the nest. This leads to increasing its share from the food, some studies found that cuckoo chick can simulate the call of host bird to get more food share. In simple form, each nest has one egg, each egg represents a solution but the cuckoo egg is the new solution. The aim is to use the cuckoo (new solution) and replace the not-so-good solution. As much as eggs increased in the nest, the algorithm becomes more complicated.

The CS is based on three idealized rules:

- Each cuckoo lays one egg at a time, and dumps it in a randomly chosen nest
- The best nests with high quality of eggs (solutions) will carry over to the next generations
- The number of available host nests is fixed, and a host can discover an alien egg with probability $p \in [0, 1]$.

A Lévy flight is a random walk in which the step-lengths are distributed according to a heavy-tailed probability distribution. After a large number of steps, the distance from the origin of the random walk tends to a stable distribution [8]. Fig. 3 shows the steps of the CS algorithm.

Algorithm 1 Cuckoo search algorithm

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- 1: Set the initial value of the host nest size n , probability $p_a \in [0, 1]$ and maximum number of iterations Max_{itr} .
 - 2: Set $t := 0$. {Counter initialization}.
 - 3: for ($i = 1 : i \leq n$) do
 - 4: Generate initial population of n host $x_i^{(0)}$. { n is the population size}.
 - 5: Evaluate the fitness function $f(x_i^{(0)})$.
 - 6: end for
 - 7: repeat
 - 8: Generate a new solution (Cuckoo) $x_i^{(t+1)}$ randomly by Lévy flight.
 - 9: Evaluate the fitness function of a solution $x_i^{(t+1)}$ $f(x_i^{(t+1)})$
 - 10: Choose a nest x_j among n solutions randomly.
 - 11: if ($f(x_i^{(t+1)}) > f(x_j^{(t)})$) then
 - 12: Replace the solution x_j with the solution $x_i^{(t+1)}$
 - 13: end if
 - 14: Abandon a fraction p_a of worse nests.
 - 15: Build new nests at new locations using Lévy flight a fraction p_a of worse nests
 - 16: Keep the best solutions (nests with quality solutions)
 - 17: Rank the solutions and find the current best solution
 - 18: Set $t = t + 1$. {Iteration counter increasing}.
 - 19: until ($t < Max_{itr}$). {Termination criteria satisfied}.
 - 20: Produce the best solution.
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Fig. 3 Steps of the CS algorithm

V.2. Mixed Linear Integer Programming (MLIP)

A mixed-integer linear program is a problem with linear objective function, $f^T x$, where f is a column vector of constants, and x is the column vector of unknowns.

- Bounds and linear constraints
- Restrictions on some components of x to have integer values

In mathematical terms, given vectors f , lb , and ub , matrices A and Aeq , corresponding vectors b and beq , and a set of indices $intcon$, find a vector x to solve [9].

$$\min_x f^T x \text{ subject to } \begin{cases} x(intcon) \text{ are integers} \\ A \cdot x \leq b \\ Aeq \cdot x = beq \\ lb \leq x \leq ub. \end{cases}$$

V.3. Particle Swarm Optimization

Particle swarm optimization (PSO) is a population based stochastic optimization technique developed by Dr. Eberhart and Dr. Kennedy in 1995, inspired by social behavior of bird flocking or fish schooling. PSO is similar to other optimization techniques like Genetic Algorithms (GA). PSO system starts with population of random solutions then keep searching in next generations till get optimum.

In PSO system particles represent the solutions, the particles start to fly in the problem space and follow the current of optimum particles. Each particle keep flying in the problem space in its own direction till get the best solution represent fitness. $pbest$ is where the values of fitness are stored, the particle swarm optimizer keeps tracking the best value obtained so far by any particle. This location is called $lbest$. When a particle takes all the population as its topological neighbors, the best value is a global best and is called $gbest$.

The main concept of PSO can be summarized as follows: at each time step, each particle velocity is changed toward its $pbest$ and $lbest$ location by random numbers generated. PSO simulates the behaviors of bird flocking. Suppose the following scenario: some birds are looking for food randomly in certain area but there is only one piece of food in this area, at the same time none of birds know where the food is. In each iteration, they know how far food is, therefore the most effective way to find the food is to follow the bird which is near to the food. PSO is used the previous scenario to solve the optimization problems, so each bird is replaced with solution in the search space and called "particle". Each particle is subjected to the fitness function which needs to be optimized giving the fitness values for each one and have velocities which direct the flying particles. The particles follow the current of optimum particles in the problem space, PSO starts with random group of particles (solutions) and keep looking for optima while updating the next generations.

In each iteration, update each particle by following two "best" values, the first one is called $pbest$ which is the best solution (fitness) obtained so far. The other best value is the obtained best value by PSO till now in the population, which is the global best and represented by $gbest$. When a particle takes part of the population as its topological neighbors, the best value is a local best and is called $lbest$. After finding the two best values, the particle

updates its velocity and positions with following equation (a) and (b).

$$v[] = v[] + c1 * rand() * (pbest[] - present[]) + c2 * rand() * (gbest[] - present[]) \quad (a)$$

$$present[] = present[] + v[] \quad (b)$$

$v[]$ is the particle velocity, $present[]$ is the current particle (solution). $pbest[]$ and $gbest[]$ are defined as stated before. $rand()$ is a random number between (0,1). $c1$, $c2$ are learning factors. Usually $c1 = c2 = 2$.

The pseudo code of the procedure is as follows:

```

For each particle
  Initialize particle
End
Do
  For each particle
    Calculate fitness value
    If the fitness value is better than the best
    fitness value ( $pbest$ ) in history set current
    value as the new  $pbest$ 
  End
  Choose the particle with the best fitness value
  of all the particles as the  $gbest$ 
  For each particle
    Calculate particle velocity according Eq. (a)
    Update particle position according Eq. (b)
  End

```

While maximum iterations or minimum error criteria is not attained Particles' velocities on each dimension are clamped to a maximum velocity V_{max} . If the sum of accelerations would cause the velocity on that dimension to exceed V_{max} , which is a parameter specified by the user, then the velocity on that dimension is limited to V_{max} [10].

VI. Simulation Results

Table 1 shows the system results after the three optimization techniques were applied with budget (B) less than 2000\$ and available 160 m² as area constrain.

TABLE 1 – RESULTS OF APPLYING OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

Method	PV Area (m ²)	Battery (KWH)	TAC for Purchase system (\$)	Total generated power by system Annually (KWH)
AGM(Absorbent Glass Mat) Battery				
CS	40.24085	9.198725	1537.4	13718.2745
MLIP	17.5290583	8.23955	954.5983	5974.7883
PSO	19.3324083	8.2053	992.4322	6589.7193
LFP (Lithium Ferro Phosphate) Battery				
CS	33.8207	3.180308	1370.2	11532.6
MLIP	17.504391	8.239325	1807.2	5966.3775
PSO	19.0481	8.239325	1841.3	6492.7699

Fig. 4 Results of Applying Optimization Techniques

It is shown from Fig 4 that the system with AGM battery, MILP optimization method has the least total annual cost, while the system with LFP battery CS optimization technique has the least total annual cost. But still the system with AGM battery is better than the system which uses LFP battery. Therefore, it is recommended the following specification to build the system under the previous constrains:

PV panels with total area of 17.529058 m²

AGM battery with capacity 8.23955 KWH

Inverter with capacity larger than 2.08104 kW (the maximum AC load power).

SolarEdge SE3000A-US-U Inverter is selected.

Three charge controllers are needed of MidNite Solar Kid MNKID-B MPPT Charge Controller 30 A.

VII. Conclusion

Three different optimization methods: Cuckoo Search Algorithm, Mixed Linear Integer Programming and Particle Swarm Optimization are applied to get the minimum TAC of a PV system with energy storage batteries. The MILP is the least cost for the system when using AGM battery in the system. But when using LFP battery in the system, the CS optimization method has the least total cost.

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